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Article

Tax Incentives as a Preventive Measure to Reduce Disaster Risk

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ABSTRACT

A comprehensive and adaptive approach by the state, all its public and legal bodies, the economy, and other entities to actively approach the possibility of implementing appropriate measures in accordance with the real flows of disaster risks to create conditions for a more effective and efficient disaster risk reduction system is a condition and a necessity of every state. Reducing the risk of disaster requires an active role by the state, specifically a response model that must also include the capacity for preventive action, i.e., the protection system's action before an undesired event occurs. In this regard, the paper will analyse citizens' stance and the potential application of tax incentives as one instrument to enhance the level of preventive measures and actions that would enable a stronger and more active role for all stakeholders in the system of disaster risk reduction and emergency management. By establishing these conditions, the disaster risk reduction system could respond more swiftly to the changing nature of disaster risks.

KEYWORDS

Tax policy, tax incentives, prevention, risk, disaster, public interest.

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1. Introduction

The activity of the state, its bodies, and collectivities that aims to collect, distribute, and spend material resources to achieve public welfare goals is called the state's financial activity, or public finance. Public state finances have the task of obtaining funds to meet specific needs in the fields of public administration, social activities, the economy, and living standards, and of distributing them in accordance with the projected goals of public needs.

The fulfilment of public needs is not aimed solely at fiscal objectives; at times, public needs are also expressed in economic, social, political, cultural, educational, security, and other spheres of public interest. In this regard, the bearers of fiscal policy have the task of assessing primary and secondary public interests and, in accordance with the anticipated course of public revenue realization, to create and execute public expenditures. Naturally, the primary objective of any government is reflected in the establishment of micro and macroeconomic stability within a system where economic growth and development, price stability, social peace and tranquillity, optimal employment, as well as an environment for reducing the vulnerability of the financial system to any form of risk and threats are present. This indicates that the distribution of collected public revenues must be created at the local level and in a manner that allows the state system to achieve its primary interests, including the goals of protecting the economic and security systems.

In economic and security theory, models for the development and protection of the financial system have been developed to establish security measures against risks and threats. Development and protection models for such a system include insurance systems, catastrophe bonds, public-private partnerships, and legal regulatory systems (Milošević & Stajić, 2022). In addition to the aforementioned models, we believe that a system of building safety protection against disaster risks could be realized through the adequate application of tax incentives. Achieving optimal resilience and disaster risk reduction requires the state to respond not only after an adverse event, but also to play an active, preventive role before and during the occurrence of disaster risks (Cvetković, 2020, 2022, 2024; Cvetković & Jovanović, 2021; Cvetković & Šišović, 2024a, 2024b; Cvetković, Renner, Aleksova, & Lukić, 2024; Cvetković, Sudar, Ivanov, Lukić, & Grozdanić, 2024; Nikolić, Cvetković, & Ivanov, 2023). In this regard, the paper will analyse citizens' attitudes and the feasibility of implementing tax incentives as one potential instrument to enhance the level of preventive measures and actions that would enable a stronger and more active role for all stakeholders in the system of disaster risk reduction and emergency management. This includes government authorities, provincial authorities, local self-government units, public services, economic enterprises and other legal entities and entrepreneurs, civil society organizations, educational institutions, scientific research organizations, public agencies, and others who, in accordance with the law, other general acts, plans, programs, and other documents, participate in determining measures and activities of significance for risk reduction and emergency management (Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, number 87/2018), thereby more clearly achieving the goals aimed at reducing disaster risk.

The subject of this paper's scientific research will be the potential application of elements of the tax system as measures for disaster risk reduction. Also, the paper aims to use scientific methods, primarily legal, economic and security theories, to examine the public's attitude towards the application of a system of tax incentives in the function of disaster risk reduction, that is, whether and to what extent the tax system can contribute to the goals of protecting citizens' property and the economy at the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels from disaster risks. The basic hypothesis is that implementing an efficient system of tax incentives can reduce disaster risks and threats and significantly contribute to raising the country's economic security.

2. Fiscal policy and disaster risk prevention

Fiscal policy, or the policy of public revenues and public expenditures, always reflects the condition of the established relationship between the holders of economic power and the general social needs of the state and its citizens. That relationship of the power holders towards public social needs

is shaped by the influence of politics, ethics, culture, customs, morals, and other factors of a specific time and moment. Historically, providing fiscal resources to meet the state's needs has always been considered a primary objective, and it remains so today. No state can fulfil its role if sufficient funds are not provided for its operations. Taxes aim to provide the state with the necessary financial resources most easily and cheaply, "and free competition will *eo ipso* enable optimal effects to be achieved in economic and social life." (Popović, 1997, p. 320).

In contemporary business environments characterized by technological advancements, taxation fulfils fiscal objectives; however, it can also be used to achieve other purposes. These other goals that can be achieved through the use of taxes are called extra-fiscal goals of taxation. They can be different: economic, social, political, security, and other (health, cultural, demographic, and the like). Thus, through the application of various instruments of its operation, fiscal policy could, in order to build security protection against risks and threats, implement a system of tax incentives, thereby creating the necessary prerequisites for the establishment of a preventive model for the development and protection of systems aimed at reducing the risk of disasters. In this manner, the risk and disaster protection model would take a new form. The current Serbian model of budget financing through the system of state aid in addressing the consequences of natural disasters and other unforeseen events (Milošević et al., 2024). would be enhanced in a manner that addresses the repercussions in this socio-economic area, not only after an undesirable event occurs but also through the implementation of a model that includes the possibility of preventive action, i.e., actions by the protection system prior to the occurrence of such events.

Prevention activities in the broadest sense express the undertaking of specific actions by the endangered subject prior to the occurrence of some "undesired" action (Baćilo, 2025; Baruh, Dey, Dutta, & Phukan, 2023; Chakma, 2023; Dada, Mohammed, & Quadir, 2025; Gajović, Cvetković, Renner, & Cvetković, 2025; Garba & Akaan, 2025; Hanspal & Bijayananda Behera, 2025; Islam, 2023; Janković, Cvetković, Gačić, Renner, & Jakovljević, 2025). In other words, we can say that prevention, from the standpoint of security phenomena and events, necessarily has the character of prior activities aimed at preventing the emergence of negative actions and occurrences. In this sense, the application of preventive instruments to reduce the risks and threats of disasters involves not only identifying risks and threats but also implementing specific measures and actions to eliminate their causes and consequences. This certainly implies a cost to the state as a prerequisite for creating an institutional system to remove the vulnerability risk threshold. This expense is indisputable; however, it must be noted that the cost is always significantly higher when addressing the consequences than when implementing preventive measures.

3. Tax incentives

Tax incentives are an integral part of the tax system and are one of the instruments of tax policy. They represent a concession - an incentive provided by the state concerning the taxpayer, the tax base, tax rates, or the amount of tax revenues, aimed at stimulating economic growth, attracting foreign investment, improving the environmental situation, and achieving a fairer and more equitable distribution of national income, among other objectives. As such, tax incentives can play a significant role in mitigating risks and disasters, particularly in supporting businesses and communities facing various challenges. Tax incentives as a tool and measure for the prevention of disaster risk reduction could be utilized through:

- *encouraging investments.* Tax relief may be granted to companies that invest in disaster-resilient infrastructure, such as water management systems, energy efficiency measures, and buildings designed to withstand earthquakes or floods.
- *building a preventive reporting and notification system.* Tax incentives may be provided to entities that invest in infrastructure needed to construct early-warning and preventive management systems.

- *training and education support.* Entities engaged in risk-prevention activities, such as education, workshops, safety consultations, or employee training, can receive tax relief to enable investment in their development.
- *encouragement of innovation.* Tax credits or incentives for research and development can support innovations in technologies that aid disaster prevention, such as early warning systems and risk assessment tools.
- *supporting sustainable practices.* Tax incentives can encourage businesses to transition to sustainable practices that reduce disaster risk, such as using renewable energy or implementing sustainable resource management.

In essence, the proper implementation of tax incentives can help strengthen the resilience of communities and all entities against risks and disasters, thereby reducing potential damage and losses.

4. Methods

A study on citizens' attitudes towards tax incentives as a measure for disaster risk reduction was conducted using a questionnaire, which was requested and subsequently collected online via Google Forms. The questionnaire was conducted between July 14, 2024, and July 18, 2025. The number of people surveyed is 214 from the Republic of Serbia. Multivariate regression analysis was used, which identified the overall scope of the assessment of the primary dependent variables (the significance of the implementation of tax incentives, the feasibility of applying tax incentives for disaster risk prevention, and the expected effects of the implementation of the tax incentive system on reducing disaster risks) that are associated with four demographic and socio-economic variables: gender, education, employment, and age. The basic hypothesis tested is that implementing an efficient system of tax incentives can reduce disaster risks and threats and significantly contribute to raising the country's economic security. The results of the research indicate that the majority of respondents support the potential application of tax incentives to reduce disaster risk.

4.1. Questionnaire design

The first section of the questionnaire included a research question about participants' socioeconomic and demographic data. The second part of the questionnaire included the following questions:

- Have you utilized the tax benefits?
- Do tax benefits contribute to the reduction of fiscal burden?
- Can tax incentives for disaster risk reduction, such as *stimulating investments, establishing preventive alert and notification systems, supporting training and education, encouraging innovation, supporting sustainable practices, etc.*, be a sufficiently stimulating benefit for the economy from a fiscal impact perspective?
- Can tax incentive instruments realistically contribute to the goals of reducing disaster risks?
- Can tax incentives serve as a tool and a measure for preventing the reduction of disaster risk?
- Would the system of tax incentives elevate the level of efficiency in the economy's response to disasters?
- Could a system of tax incentives be considered a reasonable basis for preventive action on disaster risks?
- Can tax incentives serve as a mechanism for generating cumulative resources for preventive responses to disaster threats?
- Is the system of tax incentives, from the perspective of disaster prevention, a good solution, a bad solution, or does it require careful deliberation?
- Could the tax incentive system raise the level of cooperation between the economy and citizens in disaster prevention?

4.2. Socio-economic and demographic characteristics

The sample was appropriate for the research and is not necessarily representative of the population of the Republic of Serbia, given that the call for participation in the online questionnaire was published on social media and distributed to acquaintances of the author. A total of 214 people agreed to participate in the study and completed the survey. The sample included 55.1% men and 44.9% women. Among the survey participants, 41.6% were between 18 and 30 years old, 32.7% were between 31 and 50 years old, 17.8% were between 51 and 65 years old, and 7.8% were over 65 years old. The survey included 57% of respondents with a secondary education, 36.9% with a higher education, and 6.1% with completed doctoral studies. Among survey participants, 75.7% of the employed and 24.3% of the unemployed took part. The employees participating in the survey are engaged in their work activities as follows: in the economy (23.8%), outside the economy (24.8%), in the public sector (13.1%), and in the security sector (14%).

4.3. Analysis

The paper aims to use scientific methods, primarily legal, economic and security theories, to examine the public's attitude towards the application of a system of tax incentives in the function of disaster risk reduction, that is, whether and to what extent the tax system can contribute to the goals of protecting citizens' property and the economy at the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels from disaster risks. The basic hypothesis tested is that implementing an efficient system of tax incentives can reduce the risks and threats posed by disasters and significantly raise the country's level of economic security.

5. Results

The results are divided into two groups based on the aforementioned methodological frameworks and research design:

- The citizens' views on the fact that the system of tax incentives functions to reduce the risk of disasters, i.e., that the system of tax incentives can contribute to the goals of protecting the property of citizens and the economy at both the macroeconomic and microeconomic levels from disaster risks.
- Descriptive statistics results and relationships between variables and citizens' attitudes.

The attitudes of citizens regarding whether the system of tax incentives functions to reduce the risk of disasters, that is, whether the system of tax incentives can contribute to the objectives of protecting citizens' property and the economy at both macroeconomic and microeconomic levels from disaster risks, were tested using the following questions:

- Can tax incentives for disaster risk reduction, such as *stimulating investments, establishing preventive alert and notification systems, supporting training and education, encouraging innovation, supporting sustainable practices, etc.*, be a sufficiently stimulating benefit for the economy from a fiscal impact perspective?
- Would the system of tax incentives elevate the level of efficiency in the economy's response to disasters?
- Is the system of tax incentives, from the perspective of disaster prevention, a good solution, a bad solution, or does it require careful deliberation?
- Could the tax incentive system raise the level of cooperation between the economy and citizens in disaster prevention?

The survey results show the following:

1) When asked whether tax incentives for disaster risk reduction: *encouraging investments; building a preventive reporting and notification system; supporting training and education; encouraging innovation; supporting sustainable practices, etc.*, could be a sufficiently stimulating benefit for the economy from the point of view of fiscal effect, the respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer yes, tax incentives for disaster risk reduction can be a sufficiently stimulating benefit for the economy from the point of view of fiscal effect, was given by 169 respondents. This result shows that 79% of respondents recognize the possibility of applying tax incentives in disaster risk prevention, as well as their fiscal incentive.
- The answer no, tax incentives for disaster risk reduction cannot be a sufficiently stimulating benefit for the economy from the point of view of fiscal effect, was given by 51 respondents. This result shows that 21% of respondents have a negative view of the possibility of applying tax incentives for disaster risk prevention and their fiscal stimulus for the economy.

2) When asked whether a system of tax incentives would increase the level of efficiency of the economy's response to disasters, the respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer yes, a system of tax incentives would increase the level of efficiency of the economy's response to disasters, was given by 162 respondents. The result shows that 75.7% of respondents recognize tax incentives as an opportunity to increase efficiency in implementing disaster risk reduction measures.
- The answer no, the tax incentive system would not increase the level of efficiency of the economy's response to disasters, was given by 52 respondents, i.e., 24.3% of respondents.

3) When asked whether the tax incentive system is a good solution, a bad solution, or needs to be well designed from a disaster prevention perspective, the respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer, the system of tax incentives from the aspect of disaster prevention, is a good solution, as given by 121 respondents, or 56.5% of respondents.
- The answer, the tax incentive system from the aspect of disaster prevention is a bad solution, was given by 36 respondents, i.e., 16.8% of respondents have a negative attitude towards the tax incentive system from the aspect of disaster prevention.
- The answer, the system of tax incentives from the aspect of disaster prevention should be well designed, was given by 58 respondents, i.e., 27.1% of respondents believe that it is necessary to clearly regulate the possibility of applying tax incentives in the sphere of disaster risk prevention.

4) When asked whether a system of tax incentives could raise the level of joint action between businesses and citizens in disaster prevention, respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer yes, the tax incentive system could raise the level of joint action of the economy and the population in reducing disaster risk, was given by 125 respondents. This result shows that 58.4% of respondents recognize tax incentives as an opportunity to raise the level of joint preventive work of the economy and the population in reducing disaster risk.
- The answer no, the tax incentive system would not be able to raise the level of joint action of the economy and citizens in disaster prevention, was given by 22 respondents, or 10.3% of respondents.
- The response was negligible; the system of tax incentives could only slightly raise the level of joint action between the economy and citizens in disaster prevention, as indicated by 67 respondents, or 31.3% of the participants.

The results of descriptive statistics and the relationship between variables and citizens' attitudes will be analysed through the following responses from respondents:

- Can tax incentives serve as a tool and a measure for preventing the reduction of disaster risk?
- Could a system of tax incentives be considered a reasonable basis for preventive action on disaster risks?
- Can tax incentive instruments realistically contribute to the goals of reducing disaster risks?

1) In response to the question of whether tax incentives can serve as a tool and measure for preventing the reduction of the risk of disasters, the respondents provided the following answers:

- The answer yes, tax incentives can be an instrument and a preventive measure for reducing disaster risk, was given by 166 respondents, or 77.6% of respondents.
- The answer no, tax incentives cannot be an instrument and a preventive measure for reducing disaster risk, was given by 48 respondents, or 22.4% of respondents.

2) When asked whether a system of tax incentives could be considered a reasonable basis for preventive action on disaster risks, the respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer yes, the tax incentive system can be considered a reasonable basis for preventive action on disaster risks, was given by 163 respondents, or 76.2% of respondents.
- The answer no, the tax incentive system cannot be considered a reasonable basis for preventive action on disaster risks, was given by 51 respondents, or 23.8% of respondents.

3) When asked whether tax incentive instruments can realistically contribute to disaster risk reduction goals, the respondents gave the following answers:

- The answer yes, tax incentive instruments can realistically contribute to disaster risk reduction goals was given by 169 respondents, or 79% of respondents.
- The answer no, tax incentive instruments cannot realistically contribute to disaster risk reduction goals, was given by 45 respondents, or 21% of respondents.

6. Discussion

The analysis of citizens' attitudes towards tax incentives as a measure to reduce disaster risk indicates the need for the state to respond proactively to the risks and threats posed by disasters. Thus, immediately following an undesirable event, there is a constant, uninterrupted flow of activities from prevention to response and to addressing the consequences.

Citizen responses indicate that the systematic implementation of preventive activities contributes to social stability and reduces the risk of disaster-related consequences. A significant portion of the respondents expressed the need for the state to implement tax incentives as a stimulating fiscal measure, providing opportunities for economic and other entities to take actions in the areas of investment; building a system for preventive reporting and notification; supporting training and education; encouraging innovations; supporting sustainable practices, and similar initiatives, to create the necessary foundation for preventive action against the risks of disasters. Therefore, economic and security policy makers should, through appropriate tax and security legislation, create a system of tax support for disaster risk prevention (Jevtić, Cvetković, Gačić, & Raonić, 2025; Karmaker, 2025; Metić, 2025; Petrović, 2025; Renner & Mayr-Veselinovic, 2025; Starosta, 2023; Tout, 2023; Tushabe et al., 2025).

Several respondents stated that they do not expect significant effects in reducing disaster risk through the application of tax incentives. This position may confuse. However, it must be noted that the cost is always significantly higher when addressing the consequences than the potential expense of implementing preventive measures.

The results also indicate a consensus among citizens that tax incentives are a good solution, but require careful planning and regulation within a fiscal and security framework. In this regard, the fiscal frameworks of tax incentives must align with the flows of threats from risks and disasters, as well as with the disaster management strategy. In light of the aforementioned research findings, future efforts should focus on developing legal frameworks to incorporate the system of tax incentives into the disaster management strategy.

The research results further indicate that a disaster risk prevention system could mitigate the negative economic impacts of disasters, including potential damage and losses for individuals and businesses (Aker et al., 2023). In the long term, the expected effects may only be visible after a cer-

tain period, when the tax incentive system has accumulated sufficient funds to support the smooth functioning of preventive disaster risk reduction activities.

Finally, we can conclude that the analysis of citizens' views on tax incentives as a preventive measure for disaster risk reduction indicates the need for a comprehensive and adaptive approach by the state, all its public and legal bodies, the economy and other entities to actively approach the possibility of implementing fiscal measures in accordance with the real flows of disaster risks in order to create conditions for a more effective and efficient system of tax incentives in the implementation of disaster risk reduction measures. By creating these conditions, the disaster risk reduction system can respond more quickly to the changing nature of disaster risk.

7. Instead of a conclusion

It is in human nature to have a constant desire for something better, more progressive, more stable, and safer. That unceasing flow of human endeavour for progress, for peace and tranquillity, and for new technological advancements, is always accompanied by both apprehension and fear of the events that lie ahead. In such a state of the course of human development, societies and social communities that were prepared and capable of utilizing their knowledge and existing resources to mitigate and slow down negative risk flows and threats have managed to achieve their desired objectives with slightly fewer undesirable side effects. Social communities that did not recognize their power, environment, or future trends fell into a vortex of unwanted cycles.

Each social community chooses its own set of primary goals, but what is common to each community is the creation of a relatively stable security environment. Achieving stability in a secure environment requires the active participation of all segments of society and their willingness to prioritize the primary objective. No community, no society can allow itself the comfort of 'escaping' from risks; on the contrary, keeping pace with possible challenges and threats is a condition and a need for the sustainability and development of the system of primary values of society. From there, the creation of a system of preventive action using fiscal instruments, from the perspective of the sustainability of the economic and security system, should be understood as a step taken by the holders of economic and political power towards achieving unity in the functional operation of the state aimed at reducing risks and threats from disasters.

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